

16th International Conference on Greenhouse Gas Control Technologies, GHGT-16

23rd -27th October 2022, Lyon, France

Environmental impact of pioneering carbon capture, transport and storage chains

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Abstract

The transition to net-zero emissions requires large amounts of carbon dioxide to be captured and stored permanently in geological storage. To initiate the large-scale deployment of CO₂ capture, transport, and storage (CCTS) value chains, immediate deployment of infrastructure is required. The environmental impacts of a value chain relying on ready-to-use technologies instead of optimal ones with long lead times, such as pipelines, is so far unclear. We assess the environmental impacts through the life cycle assessment of an exemplary CCTS value chain from Switzerland to Norway that only uses immediately available technologies. Even though the system relies on suboptimal technologies and is not optimized for a low climate impact, it shows the capability to effectively sequester CO₂ without emitting more during its life cycle than is stored. Contrary to previous studies, the ready-to-use transport modes cause a significant share (56.3 %) of the total global warming impact (GWI) of the value chain. More than 73 % of the total GWI stems from the use of fossil fuels during the operation phase of the value chain.

Keywords: CCTS; CCS; Life cycle assessment; Pioneering CCTS value chains; CCTS supply chains

Nomenclature

AMP	2-amino-2-methyl-1-propanol
CCTS	Carbon capture, transport, and storage
FU	Functional unit
GHG	Greenhouse gas
GWI	Global warming impact
GWP100	Global warming potential over 100 years
LCA	Life cycle assessment
LCI	Life cycle inventory
LCIA	Life cycle impact assessment
PZ	Piperazine
WtE	Waste to energy

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1. Carbon capture, transport, and storage for net-zero climate goals

Carbon capture and storage is expected to play a significant role in transitioning to a net-zero emission economy. Many international outlooks, e.g., from the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA) [1] or the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) [2], and national strategies, e.g., from Switzerland, state the need for permanently storing carbon dioxide (CO₂) [3]. By 2050, worldwide capture and storage capacities have to reach 7-8 Gt CO₂ per year, according to IRENA. Today, roughly 40 Mt CO₂ are captured yearly [1], far below the required quantities to limit global warming to 1.5°C [2]. Carbon capture and storage will have to be deployed especially for so-called hard-to-abate sectors, such as cement or waste to energy (WtE) plants [3].

The infrastructure to permanently store CO₂ includes carbon capture, transport, and storage (CCTS). While most studies investigate the whole CCTS value chain, many heavily simplify the transport stage by assuming existing pipelines. With pipelines being considered the economically and environmentally optimal solution [4], studies investigating pipeline transport give a good indication of a future ideal CO₂ transport system. Even though the pipeline technology is mature and in large-scale use in the USA, it is not readily available in Europe. Long lead times are required for planning and building a pipeline infrastructure [5], hence making pipelines a long-term solution.

Therefore, CO₂ transport by pipeline will not be available in Europe in the short term, and the transition to the long-term pipeline solution is challenging. A sophisticated and expensive transport network using pipelines will likely only be built if two preconditions are met: (1) enough CO₂ is captured to require a pipeline, and (2) the corresponding storage capacity is available. Yet, capturing CO₂ only seems reasonable if transport to the storage site is also available. To overcome this “chicken-and-egg” problem, ready-to-use transport options can be exploited, and long-term infrastructure should be established as soon as possible. Ready-to-use transport modes exist on the market, and even if the installed infrastructure is sub-optimal, early deployment is required to enable the large scales necessary in the future [6]. Thus, in the present study, we focus on CCTS value chains consisting only of technologies that are immediately available. We refer to these chains as *pioneering CCTS value chains*.

Generally, the technologies used in the pioneering value chains, particularly for the transport stage, have a higher climate impact than long-term technologies like pipelines. The climate and other environmental impacts need to be quantified. Life cycle assessment (LCA) is a holistic method to capture several environmental impacts, including the global warming impact (GWI), of products or services over their entire life cycle [7].

LCA is a standardized method (see ISO 14040 & 14044 [8], [9]) and has been used multiple times in the literature to assess CCTS chains. The reduction potential has been shown for CCTS chains where CO₂ is transported via pipelines and captured from flue gases of fossil fuel and wood combustion [10], waste incineration [11], as well as from geothermal fluids of geothermal power plants [12]. Similarly, it is shown that capturing CO₂ from clinker production can improve the climate impact of cement if pipeline transport of CO₂ is in place [10]. However, the studies only focus on mature technologies, such as pipelines and CO₂ tanker ships, for CO₂ transport [10] [11]. Under these assumptions, the studies agree that transport and storage are minor contributors to the overall climate impact, indicating the emission mitigation potential of future CCTS chains.

However, the findings are not directly transferable to pioneering CCTS value chains due to the expected increase in greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from pioneering transport modes compared to mature technologies. To the best of the authors' knowledge, up to now, no assessment of ready-to-use technology for CO₂ transport has been reported. To fill this gap, this study presents the LCA of an exemplary pioneering CCTS value chain, where CO₂ is transported from a Swiss waste to energy (WtE) plant to a Norwegian offshore storage site. All technologies of the presented value chain are currently available. The value chain's GWI is assessed to evaluate the environmental viability of the operation, i.e., if more CO₂ is emitted during capture, transport, and storage than is sequestered. Beyond climate change, the influence of the pioneering CCTS chain on other environmental impact categories is assessed.

The paper is structured as follows: the application of the LCA methodology to the presented CCTS value chain is described in section 2. Section 3 shows the outcome of the LCA, and discusses the results and their implication for implementing pioneering chains. In section 4, key points of the study are summarized.

2. Life cycle assessment for pioneering CCTS infrastructure

The conducted LCA follows the international standards ISO 14040 & ISO 14044 [7, 8]. The goal of the LCA is to quantify environmental impacts for one specific CCTS value chain that uses only ready-to-use technologies. In contrast to many previous works, the focus lies on the service of CO₂ sequestration and not the production of specific goods. Therefore, the mass of carbon dioxide stored (ton CO₂-stored) serves as the functional unit (FU), and all impacts are related to the FU. With CO₂-stored as FU, the LCA results of different CCTS value chains can be more easily compared as the results are not normalized with respect to the product of the point source.

The assessed CCTS chain connects a single point source emitter in Switzerland, the WtE plant KVA Linth, with the offshore storage site of the Northern Lights project in Norway. Figure 1 shows a schematic of the whole value chain. The flue gas emitted by the KVA Linth is considered a waste stream. It enters the system boundary of the CCTS chain without environmental burdens. As capture process, an amine-based process with absorption in a solvent mixture of piperazine (PZ) and activated 2-amino-2-methyl-1-propanol (AMP) is used [17]. With 90% capture efficiency and assuming a full-scale capture unit, around 100,000 tons of CO₂ are captured annually, depending on the exact waste composition [18]. A natural gas boiler supplies the heat required for the capture unit. While other, potentially less CO₂-intensive options for the heat supply exist, natural gas boilers are an available technology and serve as a conservative estimation following the recommendations of Müller et al. [7]. After capture, a conditioning unit compresses and cools the CO₂ to a liquid state required for transport (16 bara and -37°C). The liquid CO₂ is filled into containers and enters the transport stage of the value chain (yellow boxes in Figure 1). Electric power used in the capture and conditioning stages is assumed to be taken from the Swiss power grid.

The liquefied CO₂ is transported in standardized 20 feet ISO containers for the whole distance. Containers are an established means of transporting CO₂ in the food and beverage industry [13] and are thus available for rent or purchase. Equipment at cargo transfer locations is designed to handle ISO containers, and the pioneering CCTS value chain can rely on existing infrastructure. By using containers, the value chain can avoid waiting for dedicated CO₂ transport modes, such as CO₂ tankers for sea transport. While such technologies are under development (e.g., by Dan-Unity CO₂ [14] or Northern Lights [15]), they are currently not available for purchase. Table 1 presents the technical specifications of the considered containers, which are exemplarily taken from Meeberg Group [16]. The holding time of 64 days is assumed to be sufficient to cover the whole duration of transport from Switzerland to Norway without CO₂ being released to the atmosphere.

Figure 1. Schematic of the CCTS value chain from KVA Linth to permanent storage at Northern Lights. Only material streams related to the stored CO₂ are shown. The yellow boxes report the transport mode, distance, and fuel type per transport section.

Table 1. Technical specifications of the ISO containers used for CO₂ transport. Data from the manufacturer, Meeberg Group [16].

Parameter	Value	Unit
Empty mass	9200	kg
Capacity CO ₂	20724	kg
Initial CO ₂ pressure	16	bara
Initial CO ₂ temperature	-37	°C
Holding time without release of CO ₂	64	days

Transport from KVA Linth to Northern Lights consists of four stages: Trucks carry the containers from the WtE plant to the Rhine harbor in Basel, CH. In Basel, the containers are loaded onto a freight barge that takes them to Rotterdam, NL. A container ship brings the containers from Rotterdam to Bergen, NO, where another truck transports them to the Northern Lights onshore facility. The yellow boxes in Figure 1 show the individual transport sections with transport mode, distance and fuel. The containers may be temporarily stored at each location where a change of transport mode takes place. The storage duration is subject to the transport frequency of the previous and subsequent transport modes. It is assumed that the temporary storage does not affect the outcome of the LCA. As shown in Figure 1, all containers are returned to KVA Linth to be refilled again. The return journey follows the same route and uses the same transport modes as the outward journey.

At the onshore facility of Northern Lights, the unloaded CO₂ enters a temporary storage tank in liquid state. From the storage, CO₂ is injected into an offshore pipeline that connects the onshore facility with the subsea facility located on the seabed approximately 100 km off the coast. The CO₂ is injected into a well at the subsea facility and enters the geological storage at around 2,660 meters below sea level [19]. During the operation of the previously developed CO₂ injection sites Sleipner and Snøhvit, no migration of CO₂ from the storage has been observed [20]. Similar behavior of the CO₂ at the Northern Lights injection site is assumed, and thus no leakage is accounted for. Once injected, the CO₂ is considered to be stored permanently and therefore does not leave the system boundary.

For the Life Cycle Inventory (LCI), all equipment required in the described steps of the CCTS value chain is included. Ecoinvent version 3.8 is used as a background system with the system model *cut-off by allocation* [21]. The Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) uses the Product Environmental Footprint Category Rules Guidance issued by the European Commission. The guidelines recommend using 16 impact categories [22] which are quantified and reported in the following section.

Figure 2. Global warming impact (GWI) along the different CCTS stages (capture, conditioning, transport, storage) and the life cycle phases (construction, operation, end-of-life treatment). The impact arising during the operation phase is split into different energy carriers. Note that the impact of end-of-life treatment is too small to be visible in the plot.

3. The transport stage dominates environmental impacts

The overall GWI of the whole CCTS chain amounts to 247 kg CO₂-eq per ton CO₂-stored, as shown in Figure 2. The GWI is calculated based on the global warming potential over 100 years (GWP100). Therefore, the CCTS operation results in an efficiency of 75.3 %, i.e., a net 753 kg of CO₂ are sequestered per ton of CO₂ injected underground. From a climate change mitigation perspective operating the value chain has a positive effect compared to simply emitting the CO₂ into the atmosphere. Any improvement in the efficiency of the value chain, however, would directly increase the net amount of CO₂ that is sequestered and should therefore be pursued. With transport being responsible for the largest contribution (56.3 %) to the GWI, it seems to be the first issue to address when improving overall performance. The capture stage contributes 40.7 % and is the second largest contributor. Considering the different life cycle phases (construction, operation, end-of-life treatment), the operation phase contributes the most to the GWI (73.1 %) due to energy inputs.

The high contribution of the transport stage to the overall GWI of the chain deviates from previously published results in the literature. Literature results usually show that transport contributes only a minor amount, both in relative and absolute terms. The discrepancy is explained by the deployment of ready-to-use transport modes, with the value chain being optimized for fast deployment instead of optimal environmental performance. All employed transport modes have a higher GWI per ton-kilometer than the commonly considered pipeline. Also, a significant difference between the specific GWI can be observed among the used transport modes.

The differences become apparent in Figure 3, where the GWI is plotted over the covered distance of each transport mode and compared to the potential impact of a pipeline. A higher slope indicates a higher specific global warming impact of the respective transport mode. The largest slopes are from the truck sections, followed by the barge. Combined, truck and barge sections cover 51 % of the total distance but cause 86 % of the GWI related to transport modes. For the pioneering transport modes (truck, barge, ship), the ship shows the smallest slope and is, therefore, the most efficient in terms of GWI per ton-kilometer.

Compared to a hypothetical pipeline transport, the transport of the pioneering chain causes almost nine times as much global warming. The pipeline's impact is taken from Ecoinvent and should not be taken as an exact evaluation but rather to show the order of magnitude in GWI reduction potential if pipelines existed. Besides the difference in specific GWI, the higher overall impact of the pioneering chain is caused by the return transport of containers back to the emitter site.

Figure 3. Global warming impact (based on GWP100) of the pioneering transport chain per distance of each transport mode. The impact caused by the construction of the containers is not included in this graph. As a comparison, an onshore pipeline's potential impact for the same distance is shown (impact from Ecoinvent [21]). For every transport mode, its GWI per kilometer of transporting one ton of CO₂ is indicated.

Apart from the transport stage, the results closely match the previously reported impacts in the literature. The storage stage has a minor GWI contribution (1.4 %) compared to the remaining value chain. Capturing CO₂ is an energy-intensive process and therefore is responsible for 40.7 % of the overall GWI. Almost all of the impact of the capture unit is caused by the heat supply with natural gas. Replacing natural gas with heat from alternative heat sources can significantly decrease the capture stage's GWI impact. The conditioning stage shows a small GWI compared to the whole chain, even though it is an energy-intensive process. The compression of gaseous CO₂ requires electricity supplied by the Swiss power grid as input. Due to the low GHG intensity of the electricity mix in Switzerland, the resulting impact is comparably small.

Separating impacts along the life cycle stages construction, operation, and end-of-life treatment shows the potential for future reductions of GWI. As shown in Figure 2, the operation phase contributes the largest share to GWI due to the energy intensity of the processes involved. Using fossil fuels as energy carrier accounts for 88 % and 73 % of GWI from the operation phase and overall value chain, respectively. Fossil fuels are primarily used as heat supply in the capture stage and as fuel for transport with barge and truck. In addition to decarbonizing the heat supply for CO₂ capture, the impact from transport may also decrease in the near future. The truck section in Norway will not be operated once CO₂ tankers can directly dock at the Northern Lights onshore terminal [19], eliminating one transport part with high specific impact. Manufacturers of barges and ships already consider alternative, less CO₂-intensive fuels, such as ammonia [23], which may reduce the impact from the barge and ship sections. Besides the impact of the operation, construction is the second largest contributor to GWI. The construction of the large number of containers (407 units) causes 15 kg CO₂-eq per ton CO₂-stored. As soon as transport switches to more bulk transport, e.g., tanker barges and ships, the amount of containers is reduced, and so is its impact from construction.

The contributions to all environmental impact categories assessed in this study are shown in Figure 4 for the individual CCTS value chain stages. Similar to its share in GWI, the transport stage dominates the impact of many other categories. The truck and barge sections stand out in the *land use* impact category and show a more significant contribution than for GWI. The extensive land use is caused by the road and canal construction required for these transport modes. Additional impacts where transport has a significant contribution (even larger than in GWI) are *photochemical ozone formation*, *acidification*, *eutrophication: freshwater*, and *eutrophication: marine*. The impacts are all caused by nitrogen oxides emitted from the transport modes' internal combustion engines. The capture stage causes the majority of *ozone depletion potential* and *human toxicity: non-carcinogenic* impacts. The majority of both

Figure 4. Relative contributions of the CCTS value chain stages to all investigated impact categories.

impacts can be traced back to the production of the absorbent material AMP. The impact category *human toxicity: carcinogenic* is primarily caused by container manufacturing due to the production of the large amounts of steel required for their construction. The same reason causes the disproportionately large share of container production in *material resources: metals/minerals*.

For *ionizing radiation: human health*, the large percentage of conditioning is attributable to the nuclear power used in the Swiss electricity grid. Similarly, the large shares of conditioning and storage in the category *water use* are caused by electricity production. Switzerland and Norway produce a large portion of electricity with hydropower plants [24] with a large water use impact attached to them. However, the water use results should be treated with caution as this category has a low robustness level and might be systematically overestimated [22].

4. Pioneering CCTS value chains are already effective

This study shows that pioneering CCTS value chains can already sequester hard-to-abate CO₂ emissions today. With a CCTS value chain efficiency of 76%, the chain effectively stores captured CO₂ while emitting approximately 24% of the amount sequestered.

Contrary to previous LCA studies, the transport stage dominates the GWI of the whole chain. Due to the significant difference in specific GWI between the pioneering transport modes and a pipeline, it can be expected that pipeline transport would significantly reduce the impact of transporting CO₂. However, even without installing a pipeline infrastructure, improvements in the GWI can be expected for several reasons. Using a less carbon-intensive heat source than natural gas will reduce the GWI of the capture unit. Even though electricity only plays a minor role, the ongoing decarbonization of the power sector will further reduce its carbon intensity. If fossil-fuel energy supply to the chain is electrified, the effect of a decarbonized power supply becomes even larger. Regardless of energy supply, fewer containers are required once the value chain uses bulk-based transport modes. The GWI caused by container production will then decrease. Whether this also results in a net decrease of the total value chain GWI is subject to the specific carbon intensity of bulk-based transport modes.

Acknowledgements

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101022487 (ACCSESS project).

References

- [1] IRENA, "World Energy Transitions Outlook: 1.5°C Pathway," Abu Dhabi, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://irena.org/publications/2021/March/World-Energy-Transitions-Outlook>
- [2] IPCC, "Climate Change 2022: Mitigation of Climate Change. Contribution of Working Group III to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change," Cambridge, UK, 2022. doi: 10.1017/9781009157926.
- [3] Bundesamt für Energie BFE, "Energieperspektiven 2050+: Technischer Bericht. Gesamtdokumentation der Arbeiten," Bern, CH, 2021.
- [4] V. Becattini *et al.*, "Carbon dioxide capture, transport and storage supply chains: Optimal economic and environmental performance of infrastructure rollout," *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control*, vol. 117, no. January, p. 103635, Jun. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.ijggc.2022.103635.
- [5] IEAGHG, "CO₂ Pipeline Infrastructure," 2013.
- [6] E. Martin-Roberts, V. Scott, S. Flude, G. Johnson, R. S. Haszeldine, and S. Gilfillan, "Carbon capture and storage at the end of a lost decade," *One Earth*, vol. 4, no. 11, pp. 1569–1584, Nov. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.oneear.2021.10.002.

- [7] L. J. Müller, A. Kätelhön, M. Bachmann, A. Zimmermann, A. Sternberg, and A. Bardow, "A Guideline for Life Cycle Assessment of Carbon Capture and Utilization," *Frontiers in Energy Research*, vol. 8, no. February, pp. 1–20, Feb. 2020, doi: 10.3389/fenrg.2020.00015.
- [8] DIN EN ISO 14040:2021-02, "Environmental management - Life cycle assessment - Principles and framework (ISO 14040:2006 + Amd 1:2020)," 2021.
- [9] DIN EN ISO 14044:2021-02, "Environmental management - Life cycle assessment - Requirements and guidelines (ISO 14044:2006 + Amd 1:2017 + Amd 2:2020)," 2021.
- [10] K. Volkart, C. Bauer, and C. Boulet, "Life cycle assessment of carbon capture and storage in power generation and industry in Europe," *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control*, vol. 16, pp. 91–106, Aug. 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.ijggc.2013.03.003.
- [11] V. Bisinella, J. Nedenskov, C. Riber, T. Hulgaard, and T. H. Christensen, "Environmental assessment of amending the Amager Bakke incineration plant in Copenhagen with carbon capture and storage," *Waste Management & Research: The Journal for a Sustainable Circular Economy*, vol. 40, no. 1, pp. 79–95, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.1177/0734242X211048125.
- [12] M. R. Karlsdottir, J. Heinonen, H. Pálsson, and O. P. Pálsson, "Life cycle assessment of a geothermal combined heat and power plant based on high temperature utilization," *Geothermics*, vol. 84, no. November 2019, p. 101727, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.geothermics.2019.101727.
- [13] Linde, "Carbon dioxide | Linde Gas," 2022. https://www.linde-gas.com/en/products_and_supply/gases_atmospheric/carbon_dioxide.html (accessed Aug. 03, 2022).
- [14] Dan-Unity CO2, "Dan-Unity CO2," 2022. <https://dan-unity.dk> (accessed Jul. 27, 2022).
- [15] Northern Lights JV DA, "Northern Lights," 2022. <https://norlights.com> (accessed Aug. 02, 2022).
- [16] Meeberg Group, "Meeberg ISO Tanks & Containers," 2022. <https://www.meeberg.com/en/> (accessed Jul. 27, 2022).
- [17] M. van der Spek, R. Arendsen, A. Ramirez, and A. Faaij, "Model development and process simulation of postcombustion carbon capture technology with aqueous AMP/PZ solvent," *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control*, vol. 47, pp. 176–199, Apr. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.ijggc.2016.01.021.
- [18] KVA Linth, "CO₂-Abscheidung und -Speicherung: Chance für den Klimaschutz," 2020. [Online]. Available: https://www.kva-linth.ch/fileadmin/user_upload/Factsheet_CCS.pdf
- [19] Equinor, "EL001 Northern Lights - Receiving and permanent storage of CO₂. Plan for development, installation and operation. Part II - Impact Assessment," 2019.
- [20] A.-K. Furre, R. Meneguolo, P. Ringrose, and S. Kassold, "Building confidence in CCS: From Sleipner to the Northern Lights Project," *First Break*, vol. 37, no. 7, pp. 81–87, Jul. 2019, doi: 10.3997/1365-2397.n0038.
- [21] G. Wernet, C. Bauer, B. Steubing, J. Reinhard, E. Moreno-Ruiz, and B. Weidema, "The ecoinvent database version 3 (part I): overview and methodology," *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, vol. 21, no. 9, pp. 1218–1230, Sep. 2016, doi: 10.1007/s11367-016-1087-8.
- [22] European Commission, "Guidance for Product Environmental Footprint Category Rules (PEFCRs)," 2017. [Online]. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/environment/eussd/smgp/pdf/PEFCR_guidance_v6.3.pdf
- [23] coZEV, "coZEV - Cargo Owners for Zero Emission Vessels," 2022. <https://www.cozev.org> (accessed Jul. 28, 2022).
- [24] Fraunhofer Institute for Solar Energy Systems ISE, "Energy Charts," 2022. <https://energy-charts.info/> (accessed Aug. 03, 2022).